

OPTIMIZING THE LOCATION OF MOBILE MAMMOGRAPHY UNITS IN RURAL COMMUNITIES

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Abstract: *Breast cancer is the most common malignancy affecting women worldwide. Regular mammographic screening plays a crucial role in both prevention and early detection. One of the key strategies in the fight against this disease is to improve access to diagnostic services, especially in underserved areas. Mobile mammography units present an effective solution by enabling service provision in rural and remote regions, thereby reaching women who might otherwise lack access. However, the deployment of mobile units raises the important question of how to determine their optimal locations. In this paper, a bi-objective model is proposed for locating mobile mammography units. The first objective aims to maximize coverage of high-priority settlements, while the second seeks to minimize the total travel distance for all patients. To address the inherent trade-off between these goals, compromise programming was applied as a solution approach. The model was tested on a real-world case study in the Vojvodina region, focusing on settlements with fewer than 10,000 inhabitants.*

Keywords: *Location problem, compromised programming, mobile mammography unit.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Breast cancer remains the most prevalent cancer among women worldwide. In 2022, approximately 2.3 million new cases were diagnosed globally, accounting for nearly one in four cancer cases among women (International Agency for Research on Cancer, 2022). That same year, breast cancer led to approximately 670,000 deaths, underscoring its significant impact on global health (World Health Organization 2024, Zhang et al, 2025).

In Serbia, breast cancer is also a major public health concern. In 2022, there were 4,900 new breast cancer diagnoses among women, making it one of the most common cancers in the country. The age-standardized incidence rate was 86.8 per 100,000 women, placing Serbia among countries with a high incidence rate of breast cancer (International Agency for Research on Cancer, 2022; Zhang et al, 2025)

Despite the implementation of population-based screening programs since 2012, Serbia continues to face challenges in reducing breast cancer mortality. Barriers such as limited access to early detection and treatment services contribute to the high mortality rates observed (Todorovic et al, 2023)

These statistics highlight the urgent need for improved breast cancer prevention, early detection, and treatment strategies both globally and within Serbia. Access to timely breast cancer screening is a critical component in improving early detection rates and reducing mortality. However, healthcare infrastructure and transportation barriers limit access to fixed-location diagnostic facilities in many regions, particularly rural and underserved areas. Mobile mammography units (MMUs) present a flexible and scalable solution to bridge this gap by bringing services directly to communities. This study addresses the Mobile Mammography Location Problem on a transportation network, aiming to optimize the deployment of MMUs in a way that balances healthcare accessibility and operational efficiency.

The objective function is twofold: maximize coverage, measured by the priority of serving patients within an acceptable travel distance, and minimize the travel distance patients must cover to reach an MMU. We aggregate demand at the settlement level and introduce priority scores for each location. These priorities are computed based on demographic factors (e.g., a larger number of older patients or a higher number of women already diagnosed with breast cancer implies a higher urgency for screening).

To solve this multi-objective combinatorial optimization problem, we develop a mathematical formulation that incorporates spatial constraints, coverage thresholds, and demand priorities. The solution approach is based on compromise programming. The proposed methodology will be validated using real-world data from Serbia (Vojvodina), ensuring that the results are grounded in realistic geographic, demographic, and healthcare conditions. Through this work, we aim to support evidence-based planning of mobile health services and contribute to reducing healthcare disparities in breast cancer screening.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Souza et al. (2019) addressed the problem of locating fixed mammography units to maximize total demand while respecting the constraint that women should not travel more than 60 km to reach a facility. Only cities with existing hospital infrastructure were considered as potential locations for the mammography units. The authors developed a mathematical formulation and applied a Variable Neighborhood Search (VNS) algorithm. The proposed approach was tested on real data collected from the Minas Gerais State, Brazil.

De Assis et al. (2025) demonstrate how combining fixed and MMUs can be used to meet demand. A sequential solution approach is proposed, where the location-allocation problem for fixed mammography units is first solved using an exact method, followed by solving the routing problem for mobile units using a heuristic algorithm in municipalities not covered by fixed units. The proposed approach was tested on three different scenarios in the Minas Gerais State, Brazil. The results show that significantly more mobile units are required to fully meet the demand when the existing fixed unit locations must be maintained and users are restricted to their administrative zones, compared to a scenario where administrative boundaries can be crossed and fixed units can be relocated.

De Araujo et al. (2023) developed a hybrid NSGA-II (Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm II) for the mobile mammography routing problem with two objectives. The problem is categorized as an open vehicle routing problem with multiple depots. It involves a fixed number of depots, each with a limited number of MMUs that can be stationed there. Each mobile unit has a defined capacity and a set of candidate cities it can visit. The objective was to determine the sequence of city visits in a way that maximizes the demand for screening while minimizing the total distance traveled by the mobile units. The Minas Gerais State, Brazil was also used as a real-world case study to test the proposed approach.

Jewett et al. (2018) showed that driving time to mammography units and the number of facilities within a 10 km radius of women's homes influence the frequency of mammography screening among women. The authors emphasize that in rural areas, mammography underutilization is higher due to the lower availability of fixed facilities and longer travel times to reach them. These findings suggest that strategically locating MMUs in rural areas could increase the frequency of screenings.

Komaie et al. (2018) demonstrated that MMU implementation improves screening rates in medically underserved and rural areas. A MMU traveled through the eastern part of Missouri, serving both the urban region of St. Louis and rural areas in the "Bootheel" region. The study showed that MMUs enhance access to screening for individuals in rural locations and those without health insurance, and economically disadvantaged women.

Vang et al. (2018) provided a literature review on mammography covering the period from 2010 to 2018. They emphasize that MMUs can deliver screening services to users in rural areas and socially disadvantaged populations. To increase the effectiveness of mobile mammography, the authors highlight the application of outreach and promotion programs targeting rural communities and women from ethnic minority groups, low-income backgrounds, and those without health insurance.

Young et al. (2020) used optimization models within a Geographic Information System (GIS) to allocate women to nearby facilities where mammography screenings could be performed. In solving this problem, they considered facility capacities and patients' travel times. According to relevant models, screening capacity was insufficient to meet the theoretical demand, given the travel constraints. The case study was conducted in Arkansas, where the majority of women (80%) live within a 30-minute drive of a screening facility. However, most of the unmet demand was located in rural areas. This is yet another study highlighting the reduced accessibility to mammography for women in rural regions. Young et al. (2020) point out that the MMU's deployment could potentially address this issue.

The literature review identified a gap for future research related to the location of MMUs in rural areas, aimed at providing screening services to women living in these regions. The main criterion for selecting the location of mobile units that could be highlighted is the distance to users, either in terms of travel time or geographical proximity.

3. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION AND MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

Women in rural areas are less likely to visit hospitals for mammographic screening. To improve accessibility and encourage more women from these regions to undergo examinations, MMUs are utilized. However, deploying MMUs introduces the challenge of identifying optimal locations for their placement, as well as determining how to allocate users to each unit. In the allocation process, each user must be assigned to exactly one MMU. Selecting the best locations for MMUs involves multiple criteria. In this paper, two main objectives are considered: coverage and travel distance. The first objective aims to maximize service coverage by reaching as many patients as possible within an acceptable distance. This is done by maximizing the overall service priority, which is based on the number of potential patients in each settlement. Settlements with more potential patients are given higher priority when determining MMU locations. The second objective focuses on minimizing the total travel distance between users and the MMUs. The number of MMUs to be deployed, denoted as p , is predetermined.

The mathematical formulation of the described problem is in the text to follow.

Sets:

I — a set of settlements where patients reside, $i \in I$

J — a set of potential locations for MMU, $j \in J$

D_{max} — acceptable travel distance for patients,

N_i — set of potential locations ($j \in J$) in which a patient from node i could be served, while traveling a smaller distance than D_{max} : $N_i = \{j \mid d_{ij} \leq D_{max}\}$,

d_{ij} — distance between settlement i and potential mammography site j

p — number of MMUs that have to be deployed

$prio_i \in [0,1]$ — priority score for settlement i , reflecting the urgency of service based on demographic and health data (e.g., settlements with more estimated new cases per year imply higher priority).

Decision variables:

$$x_{ij} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if patients from settlement } i \text{ are served at location } j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$y_j = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if a MMU is deployed a location } j \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Objective functions:

$$\text{Max } Z_1 = \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{j \in N_i} prio_i x_{ij} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Min } Z_2 = \sum_{i \in I} \sum_{j \in J} d_{ij} x_{ij} \quad (2)$$

Constraints:

$$\sum_{j \in J} x_{ij} = 1 \quad \forall i \in I \quad (3)$$

$$x_{ij} \leq y_j \quad \forall i \in I, j \in J \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{j \in J} y_j = p \quad (5)$$

$$x_{ij} \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall i \in I, j \in J \quad (6)$$

$$y_j \in \{0, 1\} \quad \forall j \in J \quad (7)$$

There are two objective functions. The first (Z_1) represents the weighted sum of the covered priority scores, encouraging the placement of units near high-priority settlements (at a distance less than or equal to D_{max}). The second objective function (Z_2) represents the total distance traveled by patients to be served. All demand nodes (settlements) must be assigned to exactly one MMU, constraint (3). Constraint (4) indicates that users can only be assigned to a location where an MMU is located. Constraint (5) defines the number of MMUs that should be located. Finally, the definition of the variables is given by constraints (6) and (7).

To handle the multi-objective nature of the problem, namely, maximizing the coverage of high-priority settlements (patients) and minimizing the total travel distance, we used compromise programming to solve the created model by applying the following formula (Coelo et al., 2007):

$$L_p(\vec{x}) = \left[\sum_{i=1}^k w_i^p \left(\frac{|f_i(\vec{x}) - f_i^0|}{f_i^{worst} - f_i^0} \right)^p \right]^{1/p} \quad (8)$$

Where:

\vec{x} – decision vector (solution),

k – number of criteria

w_i – weight for the criterion i ,

$f_i(\vec{x})$ – the value of the i -th criterion for the solution \vec{x}

f_i^0 – ideal value for the criterion i ,

f_i^{worst} – the worst possible value for the criterion i ,

$p \in [1, \infty)$ – parameter that determines the type of distance (eg $p = 1$: Manhattan, $p = 2$: Euclidean)

By tuning w_1 and w_2 , decision-makers can balance the compromise between accessibility for high-priority populations and overall efficiency in patient travel distance. For example, setting $w_1=0$ and $w_2=1$ results in a pure coverage-maximization model, while setting $w_1=1$ and $w_2=0$ results in a pure p -median model. Setting $w_1=0.5$ and $w_2=0.5$ make balances both objectives. This flexible formulation allows the model to adapt to different public health policies or operational constraints based on the region or strategic goals.

4. CASE STUDY

To test the created model, the territory of Vojvodina was analyzed. According to data from the Institute for Public Health of Serbia "Dr. Milan Jovanović Batut", the incidence rate of breast cancer in women in Vojvodina was 78.9 per 100,000 women, while the death rate was 22.8 per 100,000 women (Institute of Public Health of Serbia, 2023). In Vojvodina, organized mammography screening is carried out for women aged 50 to 69 (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Serbia, n.d.). Also, MMUs provide free examinations in rural areas. For example, within the "First Mammography" project, MMUs examined 18,800 women, of whom 147 women were diagnosed with breast cancer (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Serbia, 2021). In this paper, we considered all settlements from Vojvodina with up to 10,000 inhabitants. There are 11 settlements as shown in Table 1. Those 11 nodes of demand (settlements) represent, at the same time, potential locations of MMUs. All women residing in a given settlement and belonging to the target screening population were aggregated into one demand point. An approximate estimate of the number of women who suffer from breast cancer annually in these 11 settlements in Vojvodina was made as follows: Population of women in towns (according to the 2022 census) taken as half of the total population (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2023) (Table 1); The incidence rate in Vojvodina was used: 78.9 new cases per 100,000 women per year (Dugandžija et al, 2020) (Table 1). The distance between urban settlements was taken from Google Maps.

Table 1: Input data

Settlement	Population	Woman (~50%)	Incidence	Estimated new cases per year ENC	$prio = \frac{ENC}{\sum ENC}$
Crvenka	7 232	3 616	78,9	~2,85	0.095
Odžaci	8 811	4 405	78,9	~3,48	0.116
Palić	7 771	3 885	78,9	~3,06	0.102
Ada	9 564	4 782	78,9	~3,77	0.125
Mol	6 009	3 005	78,9	~2,37	0.079
Novi Kneževac	6 960	3 480	78,9	~2,74	0.091
Čoka	4 028	2 014	78,9	~1,59	0.053
Titel	5 294	2 647	78,9	~2,09	0.070
Žitište	2 903	1 452	78,9	~1,15	0.038
Sremski Karlovci	8 839	4 420	78,9	~3,49	0.116
Beočin	8 839	4 420	78,9	~3,49	0.116

To solve the proposed model, we used ILOG CPLEX 12.1 on a 64-bit ACER computer with an Intel(R) Core (TM) i5 2.50 GHz processor and 8 GB of RAM. The model was tested on the example of Vojvodina for a different number of MMU locations. A detailed analysis of the results is presented for one example (location 5 MMUs). When locating MMU, one should aim for the MMU to be less than $D_{max}=25$ km away from users from urban settlements with a higher priority. The test results are given in Table 2. The model was tested for different values of the weighting coefficients. The first example represents the borderline case ($w_1=1$; $w_2=0$) in which the highest value of the objective function ($Z_1=0.893$) is obtained, which refers to the priority of patient service, but also the highest total distance of users from MMUs ($Z_2=311.6$ km). For two demand nodes, that is, patients from them, the condition of the maximum acceptable distance ($D_{max}=25$ km) that users are

willing to travel to be served is not met. Patients from those nodes have to travel more than 25km to the nearest MMU to be served. In the second borderline situation ($w_1=0; w_2=1$), the smallest total distance of patients to MMUs is obtained ($Z_2=149.8\text{km}$), but also the lowest patients' service priority ($Z_1=0.766$). In this case, for three demand nodes, the nearest MMU is at a distance greater than D_{max} . To achieve a compromise between these two conflicting criteria, compromise programming was used. In the case when the criteria are of the same importance ($w_1=0.5; w_2=0.5$), a solution was generated that differs by only 2.8 % from the ideal solution in terms of service priority, i.e., 2.3 % from the ideal solution in terms of the distance criterion.

Table 2: Test results in case of locating 5 MMUs

Br.	w_1	w_2	Mobile mammography locations	Number of urban settlements ($D_{max}>25\text{km}$)	Z_1	Z_2	L
1	1	0	Crvenka, Odžaci, Palić, Čoka, Beočin	2	0.893	311.6	0.000
2	0	1	Odžaci, Ada, Novi Kneževac, Titel, Beočin	3	0.766	149.8	0.001
3	0.5	0.5	Odžaci, Palić, Čoka, Titel, Sremski Karlovci	2	0.868	153.3	0.109

Spatial distribution of demand nodes (potential locations of mammograms), as well as test results for values $w_1=0.5$ and $w_2=0.5$, are shown in Figure 1. MMUs are located in 5 locations (Palić, Čoka, Odžaci, Sremski Karlovci, and Titel). Patients who do not have an MMU in their node are allocated to the MMU closest to them (Figure 1). Figure 1 shows that patients from two demand nodes must travel a distance greater than D_{max} to receive the service (Crvenka to Odžaci and Žitište to Titel).

Figure 1: Example of locating 5 mobile mammograms and patient allocation

5. CONCLUSION

In recent years, examples of various forms of cancer have become more frequent. The chance of curing cancer increases if it is detected in time. That is why it is very important to go for regular check-ups. The distance of the facilities where the control examination can be performed is one of the factors that affects the regularity of visits to the doctor. Bearing this in mind, examples of the application of mobile facilities that provide various medical services in rural areas, such as taking samples, various forms of imaging, providing therapies, etc., are becoming more and more common. The use of mobile medical facilities necessitated the creation of a model that will deal with determine their location.

This paper presents a novel location model for determining the optimal placement of MMUs, applied within the healthcare system of Vojvodina. The proposed model offers several key advantages: it ensures short computational times, achieves a balanced trade-off between maximizing the coverage of high-priority urban settlements and minimizing the travel distances for patients, and is highly practical and easy to implement, as demonstrated in the case study conducted on urban settlements in Vojvodina.

Future research directions may include the following: (1) extending the application of the model to the entire territory of the Republic of Serbia and analyzing the obtained results; (2) enhancing the model by introducing capacity constraints, which would allow for a more realistic allocation of users; (3) incorporating a broader set of criteria when determining service priorities, such as patient age, history of breast cancer in the settlement, proportion of women with health insurance, and others; (4) applying metaheuristic algorithms to efficiently solve larger problem instances.

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